

Adaptive Traffic Steering for Cellular Networks: Leveraging Predictive QoS Metrics for Application-specific Optimization

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Abstract—The rising demand of Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) applications, which require strict network performance guarantees, has led to the integration of multiple access types in cellular network architectures. To this end, the Access Traffic Steering, Switching, and Splitting (ATSSS) framework incorporates non-3GPP access technologies into the 5G network. As these traffic steering rules often overlook application-specific needs, this paper introduces a 5G-compliant traffic steering architecture that integrates Predictive Quality-of-Service (PQoS) metrics to address both dynamic network conditions and strict, possibly changing application requirements. Through a programmable Smart-ATSSS module, the architecture formulates optimized steering rules, and its adaptability is demonstrated across different CCAM scenarios.

I. INTRODUCTION

5G and Beyond-5G networks support a diverse range of applications and services, many of which have stringent network requirements and demand prioritization to ensure certain performance. This is particularly critical for Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) applications, where meeting these demands is both challenging and essential. As the demand for seamless connectivity continues to grow, efficient management of network resources has become increasingly critical. Consequently, more network operators are turning to non-3GPP access (such as Wi-Fi) as an essential companion to mobile network infrastructure.

During the second phase of 5G network standardization, the 3GPP working group integrated the Access Traffic Steering, Switching, and Splitting (ATSSS) framework into the 5G architecture [1]. This framework allows the 5G network to distribute traffic between 3GPP and non-3GPP access networks by selecting and redirecting traffic to the most suitable network, seamlessly switching ongoing data flows between access networks, splitting traffic across multiple networks, and supporting multi-access sessions across both 3GPP and non-3GPP accesses. The work in [2] evaluates the performance of ATSSS in 5G networks, highlighting improvements in user throughput and network load balancing.

Cogalan et al. [3] propose a modified ATSSS that enhances user Quality-of-Service (QoS) by incorporating network operators' requirements and the instantaneous conditions of access networks. However, this work does not consider the needs of the underlying application on the User Equipment (UE). Therefore, the effectiveness of ATSSS depends on its

Fig. 1: The Beyond-5G system design for application-specific adaptive traffic steering in CCAM scenarios involves UE, such as a vehicle OBU, which is subscribed to the network to perform tasks where the application client resides on the UE and the server is located within the data network. ATSSS rules, formulated by the Smart-ATSSS, are communicated to the ATSSS Application Function in the data network through application functions (AFs) within the control plane of the B5G architecture.

ability to balance both network conditions and user application requirements when steering traffic.

In this paper, we present a 5G-compliant network architecture that enables application-based traffic steering using the ATSSS framework (see Fig.1). This architecture incorporates Predictive Quality-of-Service (PQoS) to perform spatio-temporal network predictions across all available access networks, and a Smart ATSSS module to make informed traffic steering decisions.

This paper is organized as follows, in Section II, we discuss the system architecture and the role of individual modules, and in Section III we discuss the design and implementation of PQoS and a corresponding P4 proxy.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Next, we provide an overview of the proposed ATSSS-based architecture. We begin by outlining the necessary modifications at the UE, followed by a discussion of the adjustments made around the Data Network (DN) within the 5G architecture.

A. Modifications at the UE

To steer traffic effectively while considering both application requirements and network behavior, we introduce an application-dependent reprogrammable Smart-ATSSS module. This module decides how to distribute traffic across available

Fig. 2: The FML training on OBUs employs OBU selection based on their presence within an Area of Interest (AoI). The Smart-ATSSS needs GPS coordinates of the OBUs, in addition to application requirements and FML PQoS, to meet user requirements.

access networks by taking into account the application requirements and the expected network behavior provided by predictive QoS estimates. The decision made by the Smart-ATSSS, known as the ATSSS rule, aligns with the ATSSS rules defined by the 3GPP SA2 working group [4], ensuring that the UE’s decision is compliant with the 5G core.

Depending on the application type, Smart-ATSSS can range from a Reinforcement Learning (RL) agent trained to load balance traffic across available network accesses, to a more sophisticated system for CCAM applications that maps specific CCAM data traffic streams to access networks with better behavior based on PQoS. Case in point, consider FML (Federated Machine Learning) training on On-board units (OBUs) using an experimentation platform such as the 5G-IANA platform [5], [6]. In this scenario, a user or application wishes to train a model using sensory data collected by vehicle OBUs connected to the platform. The application can select OBUs based on criteria such as whether they have a GPU on-board or whether they are located in a specific area of interest (AoI). If the user sets a performance requirement to ensure that FML weights are transferred with high reliability from OBUs in the AoI, Smart-ATSSS can be designed to duplicate the FML metrics across all available access networks for these OBUs (see Fig. 2). For OBUs outside the AoI, Smart-ATSSS can select the best available access network using PQoS data to transmit the FML metrics, with less stringent reliability requirements.

Most CCAM applications, particularly Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (CACC), require vehicles to receive timely QoS metric predictions to adjust their behavior according to the anticipated network conditions. Specifically, vehicles can decide to wait or not to wait for a centrally calculated digital twin based on the network conditions. If the vehicle does not wait for the digital twin obtained from sensory fusion it relies solely on local on-board sensory information altering its trajectories and driving behavior.

PQoS plays a crucial role in ATSSS by dynamically steering traffic based on both current and forecasted network conditions. For instance, when transmitting CACC messages like Maneuver Coordination Messages (MCM), Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM), and Collective Perception Messages (CPM), the CACC application may prioritize in certain location specific messages, e.g. CPM, aiming to increase the input to the digital twin computation. Smart-ATSSS can leverage PQoS to ensure these critical CPM messages route over access networks predicted to have high QoS. This approach enhances the application’s performance across various access networks. More details on the PQoS module will be presented in the Section III-A.

To steer application traffic according to Smart-ATSSS decisions, we employ a custom multipath QUIC (MPQUIC) module. Built with the QUIC library picoquic [7], this module starts separate streams for each access network and binds them to the port interface using sockets. During Uplink (data packets sent from client to server), MPQUIC receives the data packets from the client, encapsulates them in QUIC headers, and distributes them across the available access networks based on the steering decisions provided by Smart-ATSSS. During the downlink (data packets sent from the server to the client), the MPQUIC receives the packets from all the available accesses over multiple streams. It then strips down the QUIC headers from the packets and forwards the packets as one stream to the client. Using MPQUIC steering functionality (MPQSFC), the ATSSS may also achieve packet re-ordering and discard the duplicates [8].

B. Modifications at the data network (DN)

We propose two modifications to the 5G core, focusing specifically on the DN (see Fig.1). First, we position a P4 proxy before the DN to consolidate traffic to/from each access network for routing through the 5G core. Further details on the P4 proxy will be provided in further section III-B.

Additionally, we integrate an MPQUIC proxy within the DN to facilitate the seamless adoption of our proposed architecture without necessitating changes to the end hosts (application client and server). The MPQUIC proxy is responsible for removing QUIC headers from packets received from the P4 proxy before they are routed to the server. Conversely, it adds the appropriate QUIC headers to the downlink packets to be routed back to the UE through the P4 proxy.

III. PREDICTIVE QoS AND THE P4 PROXY

This section provides a comprehensive description and detailed implementation of the PQoS and P4 proxy modules introduced in the previous section.

A. Predictive Quality-of-Service (PQoS)

We consider a quantile regression neural network (QRNN) that is trained to predict tail quantiles of QoS metrics addressing uncertainties associated with network behavior [9]. Here, we focus on two QoS metrics, Round Trip Time (RTT) and Throughput, where this can be extended with additional

metrics as required by applications. The PQoS module integrates time-series prediction with probabilistic forecasting by estimating upper bounds ϵ on the probability that the RTT of the k th upcoming packet exceeds a specified RTT quantile (W_R^ϵ) and the throughput over a given window size falls below a defined throughput quantile (W_T^ϵ), based on a short window of historical data. The pinball loss function is employed to train the QRNN, which assesses the accuracy of the quantile estimates [9].

The training of the PQoS module utilizes a distributed machine learning (DML) approach to minimize network resource consumption and address privacy concerns inherent in centralized training. Federated machine learning is specifically used to train the model on the OBUs of the vehicles, employing locally collected datasets (RTT, Throughput, and GPS coordinates). Upon completion of local training, the model weights are transmitted to an aggregator function, which, within the 5G architecture, can be situated in the MEC server. This aggregator function synthesizes the local models into a global model and distributes it to all available OBUs for further training. The detailed description of the FML training procedure and data collection in a standalone 5G network is presented in [10]. This decentralized data collection and training approach aligns with the 5G architecture and leverages its capabilities. Each access network trains its QRNN model using this methodology. The Smart-ATSSS then receives the predicted QoS quantiles from each access network and formulates ATSSS rules based on this information.

B. P4 Proxy

The P4 proxy is an application-specific reprogrammable data plane module positioned after the UPF in uplink direction, which is designed to merge client traffic in uplink and distribute server traffic in downlink according to ATSSS rules. On the uplink, it combines streams from multiple access networks based on ATSSS rules before delivering them to the server application. For the downlink, the ATSSS rules generated by the Smart-ATSSS are communicated to the ATSSS AF in the Data Network (DN) via application functions (AFs). These rules are then implemented by the P4 proxy to steer server traffic across multiple access networks.

The P4 proxy consists of two primary components: the control plane and the data plane. The control plane's role is to receive ATSSS rules from the ATSSS AF and write them into the data plane for execution. The data plane applies these rules to both uplink and downlink traffic. Handling uplink traffic is relatively straightforward, as the P4 proxy merges the received traffic streams into a single flow and forwards it to the server application, assuming that any packet rearrangement during merging is acceptable to the server. However, implementing ATSSS rules for steering downlink traffic across different access networks requires more sophisticated data plane programming.

An example of a downlink ATSSS load-balancing rule is mentioned below, where the data plane is programmed to distribute downlink traffic across 3GPP and non-3GPP access

Fig. 3: In a CACC scenario, automated vehicles/clients typically communicate with the controller/server using multiple message types of which we pick CAM, CPM, and MCM, with each message type transmitted as a separate stream. For instance, when the digital twin fusion requires CPM to be prioritized, the Smart-ATSSS can fulfill this need by routing CPM streams over the access network with better QoS metrics, as determined by the PQoS module. However, once streams across all access networks merge, CPM might lose its prioritization. This is where the per-packet flow handling capability of the data plane becomes crucial. By adding a rule in the P4 proxy, CPM packets receive scheduling with priority, ensuring they maintain their importance even after merging. In another scenario where a quick response from the controller is critical and the client cannot afford to wait for a response from the controller, the P4 proxy can directly respond to certain client requests from a mini-state it holds without forwarding these requests to the controller, ensuring minimal delay and prompt action [11].

networks. The ATSSS rule directs η fraction of the incoming packets from the server to 3GPP access and the remaining $(1 - \eta)$ fraction to non-3GPP access. To implement this, a random value would typically be generated, with packets being forwarded to 3GPP if the number is below η , and to non-3GPP if it is η or above. However, since generating random numbers directly in the P4 programming language is challenging, an alternative approach is used. The hash value of specific bits from the payload of each packet is generated and then compared to the threshold of η to approximately achieve the desired distribution.

Additionally, because the data plane allows for custom network optimization on a per-packet basis, the P4 proxy can implement further packet scheduling and manipulation rules if required by the application. A scenario illustrating enhanced per-packet scheduling in the P4 proxy is shown in Fig.3

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed 5G-compliant adaptive traffic steering architecture, which leverages predictive QoS metrics, effectively addresses the challenges posed by stringent communication network requirements in CCAM applications. By incorporating the Smart-ATSSS module, the architecture not only meets these requirements but also optimizes application performance through intelligent traffic steering based on real-time and predictive network data. The integration of a programmable P4 proxy and an MPQUIC module further enhances the system's ability to manage traffic across multiple access networks, ensuring seamless communication and minimal latency.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was performed in the context of the 5G-IANA and the ENVELOPE projects, co-funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement No 101016427) and the Horizon Europe Programme (grant agreement No 101139048), respectively.

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